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CONTENT AND STRUCTURE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHER'S INCLUSIVE COMPETENCE

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ЗМІСТ І СТРУКТУРА ІНКЛЮЗИВНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ ВЧИТЕЛЯ ІНОЗЕМНОЇ МОВИ

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The aim of the article is analysis of content and structure of such phenomenon as a foreign language teachers' inclusive competence. The necessity of development of such category of teachers' inclusive competence was substantiated. On the base of scientists' approaches to teacher's inclusive competence content the author has defined foreign language teacher's inclusive competence as an integrative personal background which includes the ability of teaching a foreign language to children with special educational needs together with their healthy peers in conditions of secondary schools. This competence is manifested by foreign language teacher's ability to take into consideration different levels of students' aptitudes and mastering a foreign language, different potentials of its learning, possible difficulties which students may have while studying.

The component and structural analysis of foreign language teacher's inclusive competence was made; the motivational-personal, cognitive operational, reflexive-evaluative components were singled out.

Keywords: competence, inclusive competence, foreign language teacher, content, structure.

Мета статті – аналіз змісту й структури феномену інклюзивної компетентності вчителя іноземної мови. Було обґрунтовано необхідність розвитку цього виду

компетентності у даної категорії вчителів. На основі аналізу різних наукових підходів дано визначення поняття інклюзивної компетентності вчителя іноземної мови як інтегративного особистісного утворення, яке забезпечує здатність здійснювати навчання іноземної мови учнів з особливими освітніми потребами разом з їхніми здоровими однолітками в умовах ЗНЗ. З'ясовано, що інклюзивна компетентність виявляється в умінні вчителя іноземної мови враховувати у навчально-виховному процесі різні рівні володіння школярами іноземною мовою, різні здібності й можливості щодо опанування її, можливі труднощі, які виникають у дітей під час її вивчення.

Здійснено компонентно-структурний аналіз інклюзивної компетентності вчителя іноземних мов: виокремлено мотиваційно-особистісний, когнітивно-операційний, рефлексивно-оцінний компоненти.

Ключові слова: компетентність, інклюзивна компетентність, учитель іноземної мови, зміст, структура.

Introduction. Nowadays the modern education is in the state of active modernization, one of its aspects is the introduction of inclusion ideas to the practice. With all the latitude the definition inclusive education in Ukraine the side of inclusion which is connected with studying together both students who have a normal development and their peers who have intellectual, psychic, language, speech, physical development which deviates from the norm, has got the biggest resonance.

The effectiveness of using integration and inclusion ideas in educational practice of Ukraine's secondary educational establishments largely depends on teaching staff qualification which is designed to realize them. But even on the first stages of inclusive education development the most acute becomes a problem of secondary school teachers' unavailability (professional, psychological, methodical) to work with children with special educational needs; there is lack of teachers' professional competencies in working in inclusive curriculum; teachers' psychological barriers and professional stereotypes also take place. And in this perspective the problem of teachers' inclusive competence, especially foreign languages teachers' one, as a structural part of their professional competence, has a special meaning. The necessity of this category of teachers' inclusive competence development is caused by constant increasing the number of students with learning difficulties (mostly of intellectual and speech character); inadequate preparation of six years-old students for studying at school because of the fact that learning a foreign language starts from the 1st form in all types of secondary educational establishments; the determination the reasons of students' poor progress by the teachers is not always correct and timely etc.

The problem of forming teachers' and people who work with children with special needs' inclusive competence was the subject of scientific research of S. Al'okhina, L. Antonyuk, Yu. Boychuk, I. Romanovs'ka, N. Tamars'ka, L. Fal'kovs'ka, I. Khafizullina, M. Chernyayeva, H. Shaydullina and others. The authors researched such problems of general character, as: fundamental base of forming the teacher's inclusive competence (L. Antonyuk [1], Yu. Boychuk [4], O. Doroshenko [3], I. Iskruk [5], N. Levinets', L. Savchuk [7], A. Sambor, L. Tyshchenko), inclusive competence in the context of teacher's professional standard (O. Kucheruk [6], S. Myronova, Yu. Moklovych, L. Satarova [8], N. Tamars'ka [9], S. Chupakhina [11]), teachers' communicative competence in the conditions of transition to inclusive teaching (I. Zinova, H. Shaydullina). Besides that, the scientists mostly analyzed the problem of development of future teachers' inclusive competence in the system of professional education. Nowadays there is limited quantity of scientific researches which is devoted to development teachers' inclusive competence, especially teachers of concrete subjects, for example, foreign languages, in the system of postgraduate education. But there is a great necessity in such kind of researches, and this aspect of teachers', especially foreign language teachers' professional competence, needs searching the ways of solving. It is determined by the fact that the school subject "Foreign language" is the only one which is taught in artificial conditions, when the speech atmosphere exists only at the foreign language lessons and in out-of-class activities. As our own teaching experience shows, a foreign language takes one of the first places among the most interesting, but the most difficult for learning by students. So the mentioned above needs changes the content of the foreign language teachers' postgraduate education.

The problem of development the foreign languages teachers' professional competence in the system of postgraduate education was analyzed by such authors as: I. Zymnya, K. Tabunova, O. Fedyshyn, M. Tsvyetkova. In particular, O. Fedyshyn has worked out and substantiated the integrative model of the foreign languages teachers' professional competence in the system of postgraduate education, and K. Tabunova has analyzed the professional-communicative competence of a foreign language teacher as a factor of increasing the quality of education.

The aim of the article is the analysis of content and structure of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence phenomenon.

On the base of the aim we have formulated the following **tasks** of the article:

1. To analyze scientists' approaches to the content of teacher's inclusive competence and on this base to give a definition of a foreign language teacher's competence;

2. To make up a component and structural analysis of a foreign language teacher's competence.

Exposition of the article's main material. It is worth to mention that changing teachers' professional arrangements and level of forming their professional competences are the first and the most important stages of preparing the educational system for realization the process of inclusion.

The analysis of scientific researches devoted to the problem showed that the definition "inclusive competence" in separate papers was defined "a level of knowledge and skills which are necessary for professional functioning ... by teachers of integrated schools" [3; 5].

In inclusive competence Yu. Boychuk sees an integrated and personal quality which determines the ability to realize professional functions in the process of inclusive teaching, taking into consideration special children's different educational needs, giving them a chance to including into secondary school's curriculum, creation the conditions for their development and self-development, full socialization, through direct mastering health-saving technologies [4, p. 11]. Skills which optimize teacher's professional activity in inclusion conditions give more chances for the organization of children with limited health capabilities' studying, taking into consideration their different educational needs according to involving such children into secondary school curriculum, creation the conditions for students' comfortable development, and in future – their self-development and full socialization. I. Khafizullina also gives the similar definition of teacher's inclusive competence [10, p. 8].

K. Bovkush determines teacher's inclusive competence as an integrative system of actions which lets realize professional functions in the process of inclusive education [2, p. 159] and has to be manifested in his / her work skills devoted to organization the mutual activity of different categories of students, rather responsible evaluation of knowledge mastered by students with different types of development disorders and skills to choose appropriate ways of educational influence on the students.

Some foreign scientists (I. Khafizullina, N. Radionova, A. Tryapitsyna) single out such content stages / aspects of a teacher's inclusive competence development: 1) knowledge and understanding psychological and pedagogical consistent patterns and peculiarities of children's with special educational needs

age and individual development in inclusive curriculum conditions; 2) skills of choosing optimal ways of inclusive education, working out the educational process for children with special educational needs and their peers with normal development joint studying in classes of secondary school; 3) using different ways of pedagogical interaction among all participants of educational process; 4) forming the curriculum which contributes the correction and comprehensive development of children with special educational needs in inclusion conditions; 5) realization of teacher's professional self-development according to the problems of children's teaching, upbringing and development in inclusive curriculum conditions [10].

So, on the base of existed definitions of inclusive competence we can define a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence as an integrative personal quality which provides ability to teach a foreign language to children with special educational needs together with their healthy peers in conditions of secondary school. This competence is manifested in a foreign language teacher's ability to take into consideration different levels of mastering a foreign language by students (as it is already known, not all children with special educational needs are able to learn a foreign language), their capabilities according to its learning, possible difficulties, different levels of aptitudes according to its mastering. Thanks to this it becomes possible to qualitative studying a foreign language by children with special needs during the organization the educational process on this subject in secondary school, and also for students' development and self-development in conditions of inclusive curriculum by means of foreign language and foreign language culture.

Making up component-structural analysis of a foreign language inclusive competence as a part of his professional competence, we assume that analyzed competence reflect, firstly, general requirements to a teacher as to a person with inherent orientation of a personality, values, motives etc., secondly, peculiarities of his / her activity in inclusion condition.

In the structure of teacher's inclusive competence Yu. Boychuk singles out motivational-valuable, cognitive-operational, reflexive-creative components [4, p. 25].

We meet another, functional, approach to definition of teacher's inclusive competence in researches of L. Horobets', N. Kuz'mina, S. Molchanov, O. Ovcharuk, I. Khafizullina, A. Khutors'ky and others. It consists of competence structure disclosure through number of competencies, caused by teacher's professional activity's functional aspects.

In the structure of teacher's inclusive competence K. Bovkush determines a number of mutually conditioned components: diagnostic, orienting-predictability, constructive-projecting ones [2, p. 159].

The structure of teacher's inclusive competence offered by I. Khafizullina, includes *contented* (motivational, cognitive, reflexive) and *operative competencies* [10, p. 12–13].

On the base of inclusive competence structure offered by Yu. Boychuk, which, from our point of view, is the most complete, precise and pithy, we made a component and structural analysis of a foreign language inclusive competence. So, in the structure of inclusive competence we single out motivational-personal, cognitive-operational, reflexive-evaluative components.

Thus, we think that the content of *motivational-personal component* of a foreign teacher's inclusive competence is the presence of *motives* of a foreign language teacher's professional activity in inclusive curriculum conditions (*internal*: motives of achievement, personal development and self-affirmation, promotion, material, collective's praise, prestige etc.; *external*: a wish to work with a child with special needs, to provide his / her maximal socialization, awareness the necessity of making up an individual educational plan of maximal development and together with specialists – awareness of forming a student's life activism; perception of child's problems as personally important ones) (where external motives go to the second place), and also *personal qualities* (directionality to teaching a foreign language in conditions of involving to children with peculiarities of psychophysical development to curriculum of their peers with normal development, merciful attitude to children with special needs, high positive self-evaluation, empathy, patience and endurance, tolerance to stressful situations, respect to a problem child's personality (subject-subject character of relations)).

We determine content of cognitive-operational component of a foreign teacher's inclusive competence as an ability to think pedagogically on the base of knowledge system and cognitive activity experience, which are necessary for teaching a foreign language in conditions of inclusion curriculum, the ability to perceive, change and reflect the information in necessary moment; this information is important for solving theoretical and practical tasks of teaching this subject in inclusive conditions. Yu. Boychuk notes that the system of inclusive knowledge includes general scientific, general cultural, psychological and pedagogical, and special (inclusive itself) knowledge [4, p. 16–17]. In turn, we single out methodological, psychological and pedagogical and special knowledge, which is a base for prevention of problems' appearance; these

problems can be connected with teaching a foreign language to children with special educational needs together with their healthy peers in secondary schools, and knowledge mentioned above is also a base for changing own pedagogical behaviour in inclusive curriculum conditions.

Said above let us show the content of knowledge necessary for inclusively competent foreign language teacher (table 1).

Table 1

Kinds of knowledge necessary for foreign language teachers' inclusive competence development

Kinds of knowledge	Short characteristics
Methodological	Philosophical understanding the basis of inclusive education; conception of personality oriented, differentiated teaching; theoretical basis of inclusive education in dialectical unity with society needs, time demands, and also determination the place and role of inclusive education in the system of teaching children with special educational needs, basic values and principles of teaching children with special educational needs together with their peers with normal development, on the base of secondary school; conceptions which show the unity of laws of normal child and a child with nosology's and the leading role of studying in child's development
Psychological and pedagogical	Knowledge of principles of construction the inclusive education, its system and content of educational programs and individual programs and plans: system of principles and ways of personality oriented interaction with children; knowledge of psychological and pedagogical conditions for development cognitive motivation and abilities of children with special educational needs to learning a foreign language; knowledge of psychological basis of teaching activity according to studying a foreign language by students in inclusive conditions; knowledge the basis of special pedagogy in the educational process with children who have special needs and educational work with parents, in particular during the organization the educational process in studying a foreign language
Special	Knowledge of educational technologies, modern innovative methodical systems of teaching students a foreign language in inclusive conditions; Knowledge of methods of stimulation intellectual activity and ways of general personal development of children with special needs during their learning a foreign language; Knowledge of methods, ways and forms of organization the work and managing the children's collective during their learning a foreign language in inclusive conditions

Cognitive-operational component of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence also includes professional *skills* to teach a foreign language in inclusive curriculum conditions, which we understand as ability to solve concrete professional tasks in educational process and present the mastered ways and experience of pedagogical activity, which are necessary for successful teaching a foreign language in inclusion curriculum, solving pedagogical tasks which appear during teaching this subject, ways of independent and mobile solving educational tasks, realization searching and researching activity devoted to teaching a foreign language in inclusion conditions.

We think that the content of *reflexive-evaluative component* of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence is in his / her ability to analyze the own professional activity connected with teaching this subject in inclusive curriculum conditions, in which there is a conscious control over the own professional actions' results, the analysis of real educational situations which appear during teaching a foreign language in inclusion conditions.

Mentioned above let us present the structure of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence on the picture 1.

Picture 1. A structure of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence

Conclusions and perspectives of future researches in this direction.

Everything mentioned above let us make a conclusion that a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence could be defined as an integrative personal quality which provides ability to teach a foreign language to children with

special educational needs together with their healthy peers in conditions of secondary school. This competence is manifested in a foreign language teacher's ability to take into consideration different levels of mastering a foreign language by students, their capabilities according to its learning, possible difficulties, different levels of aptitudes according to its mastering.

Perspectives of future scientific researches in the direction of analyzed problem are seemed in working out the content of structure parts of a foreign language teacher's inclusive competence, and also in theoretical and practical designing the activities which are devoted to this category of teachers' inclusive competence development in the system of postgraduate education (seminars, webinars, workshops, thematic and distant specialized courses, lessons visiting and analysis, trainings, «round tables» etc.).

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